

General Stress Responses in Insects with Special Responses to Honey Bee

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Stress is a valid physiological concept, which allows organisms to respond to adverse environmental pressures. The biological concept of stress originated in mammals, where a “General Adaptation Syndrome” describes a set of common integrated physiological responses to diverse noxious agents. One of the main elements of the stress response pathway is the endocrine hypothalamo-pituitary-adrenal (HPA) axis (McEwen, 2009). There are three stages to an organism’s acute stress response: it first detects of a stressor with sensory organs, then responds to it by defence or escape. Finally, if the stressor cannot be avoided and is sustained, the organism enters a state of exhaustion. Physiological responses to stress have been studied more recently in insects: they involve biogenic amines (octopamine, dopamine), neuropeptides (allatostatin, corazonin) and metabolic hormones (adipokinetic hormone, diuretic hormone). Multiple aspects of stress responses have been used to evaluate stress in honey bees, including behavioral, physiological or cellular stress responses. Behavioral stress responses, usually immediate response in the honey bee. Physiological measures of stress responses in honey bees include hormonal titers and neurotransmitter levels. Cellular stress responses have also been used in honey bees, since exhaustion is the final stage of chronic stress response survival rate has been used to assess the degree of stress (Even *et al.*, 2012).

Wang *et al.* (2016) found that the larval starvation caused adult honey bees to become more resilient toward starvation. Moreover, the adult bees were characterized by body mass, starvation resistance and juvenile hormone titers. These changes, in general, can help adult insects survive and reproduce in food-poor environments. This mechanism may play a role in honey bee queen-worker differentiation and worker division of labor which are related to the responses to nutritional stress. Gunes *et al.* (2017) conducted experiment to observe and examine the impact of organic acid on heat

shock proteins (HSP 70) in the brain tissues of bees. The results showed that in the groups exposed to the varroa treatments, HSP 70 results were lowest in the thymol-menthol mixture among the treated groups includes formic acid and oxalic acid. They concluded that it would be more beneficial to prefer natural medicines against varroa, which lead to lower HSP 70 results which are the molecular determinants of stress. Ramirez *et al.* (2017) explored the role of Abscisic acid in in-vitro reared larvae exposed to low temperatures. Four-day old larvae exposed to 25⁰C for 3 days showed lower survival rates and delayed development compared to individuals growing at a standard temperature (34⁰C). Cold-stressed larvae maintained higher levels of ABA for longer than do larvae reared at 34⁰C, suggesting a biological significance for ABA. Larvae fed with an ABA-supplemented diet completely prevent the low survival rate due to cold stress and accelerate adult emergence. ABA modulates the expression of genes involved in metabolic adjustments and stress responses.

Kim *et al.* (2019) analyzed altered expression profiles of Acetylcholinesterase 1 induced by diverse stress factors. In addition, transcription profiles of several heat shock protein (Hsp) genes and the vitellogenin (Vg) gene known as general stress markers were investigated as positive references. Among the tested stress conditions, AmAChE1 expression was induced under the brood rearing-suppressed, crowding and heat shock conditions. The hsps, particularly hsp70 and hsp 90, responded to seven of nine stress conditions tested, confirming that hsp expression profiles can serve as a general stress marker. Peng *et al.* (2020) tested the hypothesis that octopamine increases individual foraging effort and collective food source exploitation in the neotropical stingless bee *Plebeia droryana*. OA treatment caused a significant increase in the number of bees at artificial sucrose feeders and a 1.73-times higher individual foraging frequency. OA increases both individual and collective food source exploitation in *P. droryana*.

Finally, pursuing studies on stress in honey bees is essential for developing standard methods to assess stress in the insect of major economic importance and the development of standardized assays would improve risk assessment for pesticide and other agricultural practices on honey bee populations. Thus, knowing more about stress in honey bees is now crucial to design strategies for the protection of this fragile, but ecologically and economically important, insect.

References

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